

STUDY ON FABRICATION AND PROPERTIES OF PARTICLES REINFORCED ZINC ALLOY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p/Zn Composite prepared by means of rheological casting technology are investigated respectively on their properties such as flexural strength, impact toughness, compressive strength, hardness and wear resistance. The results show that the incorporation of Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p results in the increase of compressive strength, hardness values at room-temperature and higher-temperature and wear resistance of the materials, accompanying with the slight decrease of flexural strength and sharp reduction ($\frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{5}$) of impact toughness. The factors affecting the properties of the composites are also discussed in this paper.

INTRODUCTION

Zinc alloys because of their good mechanical properties and fine processing technique characteristics have been used in the fields of machinery, automobile, electronics and chemical industry since 1970. These alloys, however, with lower melting-point temperature, have rapid decrease in properties of strength, hardness and creep-resistance when the temperature is above 100°C , which confines their application scope. Therefore, measures that reinforcement such as carbon fiber, SiC_w , Al_2O_3 short fiber, SiC_p , Al_2O_{3p} is put into zinc alloys have been taken to improve their properties [1-4]. In this work, the fabrication technique of Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p/Zn composites prepared by means of rheological casting method is explored, and the mechanical properties of flexural strength, impact toughness, compressive strength, hardness and wear resistance are investigated individually. Moreover, the effect of processing parameters, particle volume fraction, particle size, matrix characteristics on the properties of the composites are also discussed in this paper.

FABRICATION OF COMPOSITES AND SAMPLES

Reinforcing materials used are Al_2O_{3p} with the diameter of $14\mu m$, $28\mu m$ and $50\mu m$. The matrices investigated are zinc—aluminum alloys, whose composition is as follows.

Table 1. Composition of zinc alloys used as matrix wt%

elements alloys	Al	Cu	Mg	Pb	Cd	Fe	Zn
ZA4-3	4.04	3.02	0.046	≤ 0.005	≤ 0.003	≤ 0.05	the rest
ZA27	26.66	2.31	0.016	≤ 0.005	≤ 0.003	≤ 0.1	the rest

The first procedure of manufacturing Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p/Zn composites by means of rheological casting method was to force Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p mixed into melting zinc alloys with aid of revolving energy which was produced by the blades revolving in the alloys at a higher speed. In order to gain well—bonded interface and uniform distribution of particles, Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p was often roasted at $1200^\circ C$, and some pure metal powders, i. e., Mg, Ti, were also added into the melting mixture during the stirring process. After stirring, at certain temperature, the melting mixture containing Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p was quickly poured into preheated metal mould and solidified under the pressure of $140-170MPa$, whereafter Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p/Zn composites were prepared. The microstructure observation of the composites shows that the particles were well distributed in the matrices with no defects such as porosity, shrinkage and inclusion.

The specimens were cut from the composites blanks, and machined into the size of $10 \times 10 \times 100mm$ for flexural test, $10 \times 10 \times 60mm$ for Charpy impact test, $\Phi 8 \times 20mm$ and $6 \times 10 \times 30mm$ respectively for compressive and wear resistance experiment.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The flexural experiment of the alloys and Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p/Zn composites was carried on WD—1 test machine with $2mm/min$ of the cross—head speed and the results are shown in Fig. 1. The incorporation of Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p results in the slight decrease of flexural properties of the alloys, which of the composites reduces with the increase of particle volume fraction. The impact toughness of the composite tested on X CJ—40 impact machine is shown in Fig. 2. It is obviously that the impact toughness of Al_2O_{3p} or $SiC_p/ZA4-3$ composite is 2—3 times less than that of ZA4—3, and that of $SiC_p/ZA27$ composite only 3—5 times less than that of ZA27.

Fig. 1 Variation of flexural strength of 50 μ m Al₂O_{3p} or 14 μ m SiC_p/Zn composites with particle volume fraction

Fig. 2. Variation of impact toughness of the composites with particle volume fraction

Fig. 3. Variation of compressive strength of 14 μ m Al₂O_{3p} or SiC_p/Zn composites with particle volume fraction

The effect of particle volume fraction on the compressive strength of Al_2O_3 or SiC_p/Zn composites is shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 4 gives the variation of the hardness values of the composites with particle volume fraction. The influence of temperature upon the hardness values of the materials refers to Fig. 5. The hardness values of the materials increase significantly after the incorporation of the particles, rises with the increase of particle volume fraction or the reduction of particle diameter, and reduces with the raising of temperature. Moreover, the hardness value of ZA27 alloy is lower than that of ZA4-3 alloy, but the hardness of ZA27 alloy composite is better than that of ZA4-3 alloy composite.

Fig. 4. Variation of hardness values of the composites with particle volume fraction

Fig. 5. Effect of temperature on the hardness value of 10% 28µm SiC_p/Zn composites

The composite specimens for wear resistance are run against T8 (0.8% C, the rest Fe) at 0.84ms⁻¹ sliding speed and room temperature in air without lubricant. Before testing, all specimens must be cleaned thoroughly with acetone. The variation of the wear rate and hardness values of Al_2O_3 or SiC_p/Zn composites with particle volume fraction is shown in Fig. 6. It was also found during the experiment that the more the applied load or the sliding time increases, the more is the wear volume of the specimens.

Fig. 6. Variation of wear rate and hardness values of 14 μ m Al₂O_{3p}/ZA4-3 and 28 μ m SiC_p/Zn composites with particle volume fraction

SEM OBSERVATION OF FRACTOGRAPHY

The fracture surface of the specimens failed at flexural, impact and compressive experiment were characterized by SEM - 505 scanning electron microscope. The results indicate that ZA27 alloy possesses a typical tough fracture with a lot of dimples on the fracture surface, while ZA4-3 alloy has a brittle fracture mode. When both alloys are incorporated with particles, their flexural and impact characteristics are mainly controlled by the particle/matrix interface, and the plasticity of matrices has no effect on the fractography and fracture feature of the composites. Figs 7, 8 show respectively SEM micrographes of the flexural and impact fracture, in which it can be seen that the failure of the composites is mainly along the inter-

Fig. 7. SEM micrograph of 15% 14 μ m SiC_p/ZA27 composite failed flexurally

Fig. 8. SEM micrograph of the impact fracture surface of 10% 14 μ m SiC_p/ZA4-3 composite

face. Sometimes cracks propagating through particles along their cleavage surface are also observed. Compared the compressive fractography with the impact that of the composites, it can be found that they have the similar fracture feature, and merely the impact fracture of the composites having more prominent behavior of brittle failure with more number of particles failed in cleavage fracture. Much different from the fractography of flexural and impact failure, the compressive fracture of the composites exhibits the greater deformation of the

matrices microscopically, and the tracks which the matrices were ploughed by particles to cause (see Fig. 9) It is apparently that the more the particle volume fraction, the more the tracks on the fracture surface, and the greater the compressive strength of the composites, whereas the better the plasticity of the matrix, the lower the compressive strength of its composite.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9. SEM micrographes of the compressive fracture of the composites. (a) 10% 28 μ m Al₂O_{3p}/ZA4-3, (b) 15% 14 μ m SiC_p/ZA4-3.

DISCUSSION

The fracture mode of particulate-reinforced metal matrix composites due to isotropy is not much different from that of traditional homogeneous materials. However, the microstructure, properties and cracks propagation way of the matrix alloys mixed with particles were changed greatly. As to Al₂O_{3p} or SiC_p/Zn matrix composite, there is large difference of thermal expansion coefficient between Al₂O_{3p} or SiC_p particles and the alloys (ZA4-3, ZA27). As a result, thermal residual stress arise at the interface of particles and matrices during the manufacturing process of the materials. The thermal residual stress results in the local stresses concentration at the sharp edges of multiangular particles, leading to the initiation of cracks at these places. Generally speaking, the approach to improve the strength and impact toughness of the composites is to increase crack propagation work. From SEM fractographic observations, the composites failed in two main modes: breaking along the interface and fracture across the particles, which are typical brittle rupture consuming less energy. Thus, the composites have rather lower impact toughness than the matrix alloys. With the increase of particles percentage, the fractions of breaking along the interface and /or fracture across the particles rises while that of matrix fracture descends, absorbing in less energy and causing the decrease of the impact toughness of the composites. The impact values of the materials, however, increase with increasing particle diameter, similar to the principle of the impact toughness of fiber-reinforced MMC. That is because the smaller the particle diameter, the more intensified the stresses concentration at the sharp conner, and the easier the initiation of the cracks. Besides, the properties of the matrices have certain, not significant influence on the impact toughness of the composites. Although ZA27 alloy

fractured in tough mode has impact toughness nearly 3 times more than ZA4-3 in brittle mode, there is only a little difference between that of their composites, for the failure of the composites is mainly dominated by the particle/matrix interface.

The flexural strength and hardness values of the composites reduce with the increase of particle percentage and particle size. The mechanism of these two factors to affect the flexural fracture and the impact fracture of the composites is analogous, since both failures have similar fracture features. It can be seen in Fig. 5 that the hardness value of $\text{SiC}_p/\text{ZA27}$ is higher than that of $\text{SiC}_p/\text{ZA4-3}$ and quite the contrary to that of ZA27 and ZA4-3 alloys. That is because the ZA27 matrix alloy possesses better plasticity and bonding interface with Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p than ZA4-3. The hardness values of the alloys and their composites are outstandingly reduced while the test temperature is risen. The descending degree of the hardness values is nearly same for the alloys and their composites. Therefore it can be said that the descending of the hardness values of the composites with temperature is attributed to the matrices, namely, the particles still play a reinforcing role in the temperature scope studied in this work. It is indicated that the addition of Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p , improving the high-temperature resistance of ZA27 and ZA4-3 alloys, brings about the hardness value of $\text{SiC}_p/\text{ZA27}$ at 100°C equal to that of ZA27 at room temperature, which supplies an effective way to broaden the application ranges of these alloys.

The compressive failure of the composites is caused actually by dislocation movement in certain direction. Consequently, all measure contributed to impede the moving of the dislocation in the materials will be advantageous to increase their compressive strength. The composites with smaller size or larger percentage of the particles, having a stronger impediment to dislocation movement and capability to resist deformation, gain higher compressive strength and hardness values.

The addition of stiffer ceramic particles (Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p) into the softer alloys (ZA27 and ZA4-3) constitutes a superior soft-stiff coordination, reducing the possibility of the adhesion to occur, and increasing the hardness values of the materials. Thus Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p/Zn composites exhibit a fine wear resistance. The hardness values of the composites increase with increasing the content of the particles or lowering the particle size, simultaneously their wear rate is also improved (see Fig. 7), which corresponds to the adhesive wear principle of metals.

$$W = K \frac{N}{H}$$

Where W is wear volume, H the surface hardness of testing materials, N vertical load, K wear coefficient. When severe adhesion takes place to the composites, however, the wear resistance of the composites almost has nothing to do with the hardness value of the materials at room temperature, only dependent on the melting point of the matrices. Clearly, the properties of the matrix alloys have an important effect on the wear rate of the composites. In addition, increasing applied load and extending sliding time produce much heat on the wearing surface at the occasion of no lubricant, which makes the materials soften and adhesion occur

easily, undoubtedly causing the raising of the wear rate. The effect of applied load and sliding time on the wear resistance of the composites is as same as reported in the literature[5].

CONCLUSION

(1) The flexural and impact fracture of Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p/Zn composites prepared by means of rheological casting technology are mainly dominated by the particle/matrix interface. With the increase of particle volume fraction, the flexural strength and impact toughness of the composites decrease. Under the same particle and matrix conditions, the bonding strength of the particle/matrix interface, thermal residual stress at the interface and particle volume fraction are major factors upon the flexural and impact properties of the composites.

(2) The hardness values, compressive strength and wear resistance of the composites rise with the increase of particle volume fraction or the decrease of particle size. The raising of test temperature results in the rapid descending of the hardness values of the composites and the alloys. However, the addition of Al_2O_{3p} or SiC_p improves the property of high temperature resistance of ZA27 and ZA4-3 alloys significantly.

(3) The properties of the matrices as well as the bonding strength of the interface, particle volume fraction and thermal residual stress at the interface, have certain effect on the properties of the composites.

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MODELLING: POLYMER MATRIX MATERIALS
